

REVIVING THE GANDHIAN ASHRAM MODEL: A SUSTAINABLE PATHWAY TO ECOLOGICAL BALANCE

Ankit*

Research scholar, Dept. Gandhian thought and Peace Studies, School of Social Science, Central university of Gujarat, Kundela, Email id: ankit.bu10@gmail.com

Dr. Janak Singh Meena**

Professor, Dept. Gandhian thought and Peace Studies, School of Social Science, Central university of Gujarat, Kundela, Email id: janak.meena@cug.ac.in

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Abstract

The environmental issues as we understand today was not the same at the period of Gandhi, his thoughts and ideas on development, gram swaraj, non-violence, self-reliant, Sarvodaya (welfare of all) and Antodaya (upliftment of the weakest) etc. disclose his environmental perspective. Gandhi's thoughts inspired diverse streams of environmental philosophy, emphasizing harmony with nature, responsible resource use, and community-centric sustainability. This paper is an attempt to examine the theoretical aspect of Gandhian environmentalism and primarily examine Gandhi's ashrams functioned as experiments in living simply, minimizing waste, conserving resources, and fostering collective responsibility for the environment. The paper seeks to present an analysis of case studies around the environmental movement, through a Gandhian lens. It argues that Gandhi's environmental perspective remains relevant in contemporary times.

Keywords: *Gandhi philosophy, Environment, Ashram Model, Materialistic-world, Self-reliance*

Introduction

The present world in which science, technology and development play a crucial role in changing human history. However, to much exploitation of natural resources in the name of development and human greed leads to a serious environmental problem. In fact, the idea of development is itself more controversial in the contemporary situation as it often justifies the unethical use of natural resources. It's rather common to encounter high dam controversies,

deforestation, water disputes and air pollution these days. Eminent environmental activist 'Vandana Shiva argues that development is actually based on a continuation of colonialism.' according to Gustavo Esteva, she argues that "development is a permanent war waged by its promoters and suffered by its victims" (Shiva, 1995). that a true science that does not respect nature's needs and a development which does not respect people's demands threatens human survival. The environment of Gandhi gives us a new vision to harmonise nature with the needs of people (Joshi, 2001).

Gandhi was far more than just a freedom fighter; his remarkable and charismatic personality encompassed many dimensions. His thoughts and teachings continue hold deep relevance across the wide range. Including education, Socio-political, economics, science-tech, philosophy, value and ethics, global peace and harmony and Enviornmental sustainability. His visionary ideas consistently as an inspired and motivated people and shaping society (Dutta, 2023). He considers mother earth a living organism. He believed "that the universe was structured and informed by the cosmic spirit, that all men, all life and indeed all creation were one" (Parekh, 2001). Gandhi's lifelong experimentations with truth led him to develop all his ideas and thoughts, which makes Gandhian ideas even more relevant in modern time.

People's mobilization of the environment has increase in the last five decades or so. There have been environmental conventions at all over the globe, for instance the "Stockholm Conference" held in 1972 and the "Rio Earth Summit" of 1992 (Giri, 2023). However, Gandhi voiced his concern for the environment in his different publications, speeches, and messages to the people about a decades ago (Dutta, 2023). It is important to keep in mind that he was not an environmentalist in the contemporary sense, but the implications of his socio-political and economic ideas make him an environmentalist. Though several environmentalist thinkers and movements in India have drawn inspiration from Gandhi.

Although Gandhi never employed words like "environment" or "ecology" a deep respect for nature was woven throughout his life, life, philosophy and work. whether his idea of gram-swaraj, non-violence, khadi Charkha to his self-reliance, the presence and importance of the natural world were always in heart of Gandhi. For this reason, Pravin Sheth said that "World's Early Environmentalist in Vision and Practice" in his work "The Eco-Gandhi and Ecological Movements." Sundarlal Bahuguna, the leader of India's first successful environmental Chipko movement in 1973, and Medha Patekar, the leader of the Narmada Bachao campaign in the 1980s, were both inspired by Gandhi (Dutta, 2023).

Gandhi as Environmentalist

Gandhi has not said anything specific on environmental issues, as in earlier times it was not a big concern and issue for mankind or society. The irony is that, whereas every responsible person appears to be aware and worried about pollution, no substantial remedy is in sight. Gandhi's have offered a new way of approach about how to balance human demands with the environment. His reflection about Satyagraha, simple living, and development show case how society can grow in a way that it doesn't harm nature and other human's beings (Giri, 2023). He has faith in *Advaita* philosophy of nonduality, which holds that man and all living things are inherently one. "Nature has enough to satisfy everyone's needs but not to satisfy anybody's greed," he said, and this became a key premise of modern environmentalism. Here, Gandhi's teachings provide some hope. When we see his literature, speech and writings, we find everything about it is ideas on the environment (Joshi, 2003).

Gandhi's book *Hind swaraj* 1909, is not only provided as a "critique of modern civilisation and Western industrialization but also an insightful work laying the groundwork for environmental consciousness. Although the term "environment" as we know it today was not in common use during Gandhi's era, the philosophies within *Hind Swaraj* contain key principles relevant to today's global ecological debates. Gandhi was deeply critical of modern civilisation, viewing it as a leading cause of environmental issues. He warned against the dangers of reckless and unplanned industrial and modernization growth, which he described as "Satanic" for its unrelenting pursuit for material wealth and its incessant growth of desires. He believes that such activities led to widespread resource exploitation and upset the natural balance between humans, and the environment is highly relevant considering present-day fears about exhaustion of resources and environmental degradation. In the Morden tradition seen human nature with environment is separated or conquerors, whereas as Indian tradition human nature with environment is interconnected and respectful. the ground was his mother and should be revered. Gandhi was deeply impacted by Indian tradition and emphasized simple living and high thinking. Gandhi believed that "*the Earth provides enough to satisfy human needs but not human greed*", making a clear distinction between need and want. He argued that only by exercising self-restraint and limiting desires can humanity live in balance with nature, emphasized on the interdependence of all living things and promoted respect and awe for all beings, including plants, animals, and non-living things like rivers and mountains. The *swaraj* means self-rule extending to the ideas of *gram swaraj*, where villagers live in harmony and cooperation with natural resources sustain as a common and collective good.

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Gandhi's autobiography "*The Story of My Experiments with Truth (1925-29)*" though primarily a spiritual, moral and ethical journey, gently represents his deep understanding of the environment. Through personal highlight, Gandhi proves how living simply-life, limiting one's needs/demands, and practicing self-restraint are essential for harmony with nature. His daily practicing vegetarianism, homespun clothing and minimal possessions, were expressions of both personal and environmental discipline. For example, Gandhi's prayer speech at Sambhal on 27th Dec 1947 he said "You must keep yourself clean externally and internally. Your village should be free of dirt and dung in every way. And it should be free from foul smells. You should follow the rules of sanitation" (Joshi, 2001). He motivates Indian villagers to sanitation and cleanliness of the environment (vol. 90, pp 305-307). Moreover, Gandhi once said, "Man has no power to create life, therefore, he has no right to destroy life" (Suchak., n.d.). Man has been endowed with superior faculties, helping him to experience compassion toward inferior beings.

Gandhi's book "*Key to Health (1948)*" highlights the environmental perspective focused on Natural Cure, and Gandhi's ideas of unity with all living beings, rooted in frugal natural resources use, aimed to contribute to a sustainable society through practical application of real-life concepts. He emphasises a close link between men and the environment. In ancient Indian culture, plants, rivers, mountains, sunlight, and so on, were considered holy and given great importance due to their health benefits. "The science of natural therapeutics is based on a use of the same five elements, in the treatment of disease, which constitute the human body. These are earth, water, ether, sunlight and air... they can be utilized for health purposes" (Key to Health, pp.57-58).

This is also closely related to village life, which Gandhi strongly advocate for, 'My natural cure is designed solely for villagers and villages. There is no place in it for a microscope, X-ray, and similar things. Personal hygiene and healthy living are of primary importance' (Harijan, 11-8-1946). According to Gandhi, human's body asserts from five natural elements, the most significant among them air element. He disliked violating these elements that leads to an unhealthy lifestyle. (*Gandhi's views on nature and environment*, n.d.). His opinion in Harijan, 'Anyone who fouls the air by spitting about carelessly, throwing refuse and rubbish or otherwise dirtying the ground sins against man and nature. Man's body is the temple of God. Anyone who fouls the air that is to enter that temple desecrates it' (Harijan, 7-4-1946).

Gandhi deeply advocated for simple and *Sattvic* (clean and healthy) diet as necessary for good health. He was a great believer in vegetarianism and strongly opposed eating meat. According

to Gandhi, human beings are more than their physical bodies; the spirit and moral qualities are also noteworthy. He believed that humans were not naturally designed to eat meat, but rather to thrive on the fruits and plants that the earth frequently provides. Even when faced with illness, Gandhi refused to renounce his beliefs, instead staying to vegetarianism and natural healing treatments. His devotion to natural cure and unwillingness to consume meat can be interpreted as reflections of his deep compassion and commitment to nonviolence, not only toward other people, but toward all species that exist. For Gandhi, caring for one's health was inseparable to living gently and ethically on this earth, in harmony with both nature and the wider ecosystem of life.

Gandhi's Ashram model

Gandhi's ashram model is based on his teaching to improve the human condition from spiritual, moral and ethical in contrast with the capitalistic form of humans. The ashram model is a perfect example of our contemporary civil society. Every person who lived in an ashram did their own duty. no inequality, injustice, no discrimination based on gender, race, colour, caste etc. as "each man doing their own duty" is a simple method to resolve a problem and issues in society. His ashram model also creates an oceanic influence theory to other people also throughout the change toward *individual* → *family* → *society* → *division* → *state* → *nation* and lastly at *universal level*. In this theory, focus is shifted on the smaller unit of the society, though ultimate change is being done to forward to the upper and hierarchical level and this transformation is based on justified ends and its means. Gandhi established several ashrams throughout his life, both in India and South Africa. First Phoenix Settlement in Natal 1904, Second Tolstoy Farm outside Johannesburg in 1910, after Gandhi came to India, he established third Sabarmati Ashram outside Ahmedabad in 1915, and fourth Sevagram Ashram established in Wardha 1936 (Hardy, n.d.,).

Many thinkers analyse Gandhi's ashram model in several of their works, according to Mark Thomson in his remarkable book *Gandhi's initiatives of ashram life thus: analysis* "The ashrams Gandhi established served as laboratories where he and his colleagues experimented with nonviolence as an alternative way of life. In these small monastic communities of men and women living according to absolute vows he sought to lay the groundwork for an egalitarian social organisation and economy, and to develop an education system that reflected Indian society. The ashrams model provided economic and moral support as well as fostering the discipline and awareness necessary for their members to sustain grassroot civil disobedience. Gandhi saw the need in the tradition-bound, rigidly hierarchical Indian society,

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for a moral sanction able to inspire people to help themselves. He believed ashramas life, based on mutuality, simplicity and hard work, would nurture an asceticism that could be channelled through positive action to reform society" (Thomson, 1993).

Gandhi's ideas of an ashram life were heavily influenced by John Ruskin's work and his strict vows of vegetarianism. He adhered to his moral principles throughout his life not only because of his family background and traditions, but because he kept his promise to his mother. In addition to his non-violent approach, this might have contributed to his success. Throughout his works, Leo Tolstoy emphasizes the importance of self-control and vegetarianism, which is reflected in Gandhi's ascetic lifestyle. Ashram life is based on eastern and Indian values, which align with Gandhi's ideas on cooperative communities. While living in South Africa, he participated in non-violent struggles against racial discrimination in cooperative communities. Community living allowed Gandhi to involve everyone in his life mission, extending his non-violence into all spheres of life (*Gandhi's ashrams: seed beds of ecological development*, n.d.).

Case study of Indian environmental movement

The Indian environmental movement in recent years has focused on a wide range of issues from waste management, climate change, environmental clearance, wildlife, and forest conservation to pollution, illegal mining and disposal of toxic wastes. To address those concerns, modern activists adopt Gandhian philosophy of nonviolence and community development for grassroots mobilization on eco-friendly governance. Modern environmental movements are increasingly concerned with green politics and the conservation of natural resources. The history behind India's environmental movement is the rich tapestry of battles, protests and tenacity. From the colonial era of exploitation to the challenges of the globalization era and climate change, the progress has been markers in the sand and people's mobilization. As we analyse the growth of this movement, it becomes clear that Gandhi's values continue to inspire and inform the ongoing quest for ecological sustainability and social justice. Key concepts and principles of Gandhi's philosophy are Sarvodaya (welfare of all), satyagraha (force of truthness), ahimsa (non-violence), and self-sufficiency etc. As environmental activists apply Gandhian philosophy to contemporary environment movements, they can create a framework that addresses environmental concerns as well as promoting social justice, empowerment, and ethical engagement and sustainability with nature. some environmental movement related to Gandhian philosophy: -

- **Chipko Movement (1973):** The Chipko movement, protest against cutting trees in the Himalaya region, especially women leading the charge by Chipko means to hug trees

to prevent their felling. The movement was fully inspired by Gandhian philosophy of non-violence, satyagraha, underlining the role of rural masses in environmental conservation. Chandika Prasad Bhatt proclaimed Gandhi as the spiritual patron of the movement and said, "Like Gandhiji, he calls for a break with the culture of domination and for redefining our roles in sharing the fruits of our toil with others, with one another and with nature" (Chipko movement, 2025).

- **Narmada Bachao Andolan (1985):** This movement emerged from Madhya Pradesh in 1985, Inspired by Gandhian concepts of justice and civil disobedience, the protesters sought to preserve values of human rights and ecological sustainability. Leaders such as Medha Patekar and Baba Amte remembered Gandhi's criticism of modern civilisation, large-scale development as they worked against the exploitation of tribal and rural people displaced by development projects. This generation looks for alternative, decentralized and environment-friendly sustainable ways, influenced by Gandhian philosophy (Moolakkattu J. S., 2019).
- **Silent Valley Movement (1970):** this movement originated from Kerala in the late 1970s, The Silent Valley rainforest was saved by activists through Gandhian ethics forms of non-violent protest, public awareness, mass mobilization etc This holistic approach brought together a variety of interests, and reflected Gandhi's respect for all beings and the victory of values over short-term economic profit. The outcome of this movement shifted toward recognizing ecological stability (Sasikala, n.d.).
- **Rally for Rivers (2017):** This movement mainly focuses to raise awareness about the politeness of India's rivers and promote sustainable water management. It reflects Gandhian values and philosophy of environmental conservation and collective responsibility toward helping to save natural resources.
- **Plastic Waste Management Campaigns:** In India, there are several regional campaign initiatives aimed to create a plastic free environment, minimum and zero uses of plastic day to day uses. These movements promote Gandhian values of simplicity and self-reliance, encouraging communities to adopt eco-friendly practices.

Hence, these movements demonstrate how Gandhian philosophy continues to inspire environmental activism in India, promoting a holistic approach that combines ecological sustainability with social justice and community empowerment.

Contemporary Relevance of Gandhi's Environmental Perspective

Gandhi's ecology, conceived well before the contemporary ecology movement, can be eminently useful in climates of environmental problems, environmental detriment, and growing inequalities in the contemporary age. Gandhi's passionate appeals for simplicity and self-restraint, his aphorism "nature provides for human needs, not for greed" have a direct resonance with today's anxiety over overconsumption, unsustainable way of life, and the wanton exploitation of nature. Inspired by his notion of Sarvodaya (welfare of all) and antodaya (upliftment of the poorest), his idea has significantly informed contemporary environmental justice debates by promoting a development process which is not merely environmentally harmless, but socially inclusive as well. Gandhi's principle of nonviolence (ahimsa) included animals, according to his choice of diet and own account and is inviolable in his own eyes; Gandhi also struggled to guarantee animals rights and biodiversity. In the wake of global natural calamities, villages are looking at decentralisation, solid local food networks, and self-reliance. Suddenly, Gandhi's village swaraj (local self-reliance) becomes relevant, his ashram experiments are early templates of holistic living and common management.

Post independence Indian environmentalism that took to Gandhian methodology and teachings such as Chipko Andolan and Narmada Bachao Andolan and Silent valley movement The relevance of non-violent direct action and bottom up organizing and moral bond to the land in the face of exploitative development. Gandhi's scepticism of over-mechanisation/industrialisation and the reckless promotion of technologies, corresponds with current debates of runaway environmental costs of economic growth and an urgent need for humane, moral and regenerative innovation. The focus on hygiene, clean water and public health at the policy level, is contagious even today with schemes such as the Swachh Bharat Abhiyan for Clean India Campaign. Even more, his ethic of individual responsibility, in small acts and daily practice, from conserving resources to recognizing the natural world's inherent value, is no less important in the struggle to reclaim our earth today.

Ultimately Gandhi's environmental vision finally calls on people to reclaim an ethics of care, simplicity, and sustainability, emphasizing the fact that for our worldwide crisis to be resolved, we need more than just technical fixes; we need a change of beliefs, relationships, and ways of living as well. Hence, in the contemporary times with increasing environmental challenges, Gandhi's ideas seem not only relevant but also act as a transformational model for creating a just, sustainable, and peaceful future for all living beings on earth.

Conclusion

The present environmental hazards that have gripped the world need an immediate and effective sustainable strategy to insure the healthy and peaceful existence of living beings. The Gandhian perspective gives us sufficient opportunities to overcome the crises. It may not be possible for today's generation to live a Spartan lifestyle, but rationality and sensibility toward putting these ideas into practice would help save the earth. Environment friendly science and technologies adopted by people. His ashram model is sufficiently helpful and solves the environment issues, mobilising people towards saving the environment system. This kind of change to a smaller unit to a bigger one in the society. Contemporary governments also make schemes, for example, the focus on hygiene, clean water and public health at the policy level, is contagious even today with schemes such as the Swachh Bharat Abhiyan for Clean India Campaign and Odd-Even traffic policy for decrease air pollution. Moreover, Gandhi's ideas are sufficiently relevant in the present context to resolve environmental concerns.

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